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of Geological Heritage

ProGEO SW Europe Regional Working Group

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ABSTRACTS BOOK

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Session 2: Geoheritage assessment and methods

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Mapping the geological heritage related to the Cliffs of Lumignano geosite (lower Oligocene, Northern Italy)

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Introduction

The identification, preservation, and valorisation of Geoheritage, i.e., those geological features that testify for the history and evolution of Earth, are being increasingly recognized as tasks of the Earth Scientist with a significant impact on economy and society. Most nations maintain a catalogue of their geodiversity, and there are specific categories of UNESCO which are concerned with geoheritage and related topics, as the Global Geoparks, and those Natural World Heritage Sites which were nominated according to criterion VIII.

Yet, the identification of geoheritage and geodiversity as a worthy sub-discipline of the Earth Sciences is recent. The term and concept of "geodiversity" only dates to the 1990s (Gray, 2008). And consequently, elements of geodiversity are not usually mapped yet.

Maps reporting elements of the geological heritage are, however, becoming common, and those nations which have consolidated geoheritage inventories usually have it mapped on web-gis applications (e.g., Martin et al., 2014). Meanwhile, the question of how geoheritage should be mapped is still open and lively debated. Contributions on mapping of geoheritage mostly stem from the strict relationship that undoubtedly exists between geodiversity and landscape, and thus, the current debate is on how geomorphosites (i.e., prominent geodiversity sites with geomorphological value) should be mapped (e.g., Coratza et al., 2021). However, while all geodiversity sites are part of a landscape, their main value is not always geomorphological, nor they always have a straightforward relationship with the landscape they fit in. In some cases, geodiversity sites bear no connection with the landscape at all.

We present the geological map of a portion of the Berici Hills (Vicenza, Northeastern Italy) with a high geodiversity, that has been known and studied since the nineteenth century at least, and in which geoheritage values are mostly unrelated to landscape.

This map is not intended for the use by the public. Rather, it is designed for geotourism operators and local administrations, and provides a database for future projects of valorization and protection of geoheritage. While not being a geotouristic map in itself, maps for the general public or other geotouristic outputs may be obtained from it through simplification or modification.

Study area and its cultural geoheritage

The area of Lumignano is in Northeastern Italy, on the eastern flanks of an isolated group of hills topped by a karst plateau, the Berici Hills (Fig. 1). It is best known as a climbing area, where climbing has been performed on natural cliffs up to 60 m tall for decades. Lumignano, and the nearby village of Costozza, are both hamlets of Longare, a municipality with less than 10000 inhabitants.

The area has been the object of geological studies at least since the eighteenth century (Fig. 2), when Arduino visited the quarries of Costozza (Arduino, 1760). Costozza and Lumignano were also referred to in the treatise of architect Vincenzo Scamozzi "L'idea dell'architettura universale" (1615), because of the quarries of Vicenza Stone. In its Four Books of Architecture (1570), Palladio used the term "pietra tenera" (i.e., soft stone) for dimension stones quarried in Oligocene limestones near Vicenza and identified the building stones of bridges in the city of Vicenza as being from "Costozza". The underground limestone quarries in Costozza have been active since before the Roman times.

Figure 1. A) landscape of San Cassiano e Brojon cliffs; B) San Cassiano cliffs, hermitage and caves.

Stratigraphic succession

A upper Eocene to lower Oligocene shallow water carbonate succession crops out in the region, which is terminated by a major karst unconformity, probably of late Oligocene age; scanty and discontinuous quartz sand and gravel, possibly late Oligocene to Pliocene in age, occur locally above the unconformity; layered volcanic tuff deposits are intercalated with the Oligocene limestones, and the upper Eocene-lower Oligocene carbonate succession is cut by volcanic dikes and eruption conduits, filled with basalts and intradiatremic breccia.

The lower Oligocene limestone belongs to the Castलगomberto Formation, which has been interpreted as being deposited in a carbonate platform with coral reefs. However, interpretations of the sedimentary environment of this platform are divergent in the literature. The main geosite of the area, i.e., the Cliffs of Lumignano, testifies for the Rupelian paleogeographic arrangement of the region, and for the onset of a large coral reef system. Frost (1981) interpreted the Oligocene platform of the Berici Hills as having a sheltered lagoon, and a discontinuous coral reef ridge. Nebelsick et al. (2013) evidenced instead the presence of a ramp environment dominated by coralline red algae.

Results

We endeavoured a detailed geological mapping of the Lumignano area (Fig. 3), aimed at clarifying the depositional setting of the Castलगomberto Formation. Facies analysis on >150 polished slabs and thin sections, and field

relationships between sedimentary units, have been used to define five different facies associations in the Oligocene Castelgomberto Formation.

Figure 2. historical lithography of Costozza quarry (Pigafetta Antonio, 1974).

From the landward side, the first facies encountered is a layered grainstone-rudstone facies with fragmented red algal thalli and benthic foraminifera, mostly miliolids representing a seagrass meadow deposit. Locally, intercalations of layered tuffs and tuffites. On the cliffs, the dominant facies is a coral boundstone facies, massive, with corals in living position in a fragmented red algal rich grainstone-packstone matrix. In front of these bodies, coralline algal facies occur in which primary components are coralline red algae, small nummulites and bryozoans. In the south-eastern part of the hills, another facies occurs, the Pietra di Vicenza facies, which is a porous, well-sorted grainstone with fragmented red algal thalli and foraminifera. At the outermost side, a marl and fine packstone facies is found, its components being mostly bryozoans, echinoderms and planktic foraminifera.

All these facies deposited at the same time, and they have lateral relationships both along dip of the carbonate platform profile, and along strike. Overall, they fit into a distally steepened carbonate ramp depositional system. The inner ramp was dominated by a euphotic seagrass meadow. Towards the open sea, there was a coral reef system interdigitated seaward with oligophotic maerl deposits. Moving along dip, rhodoliths become more rounded and form a ca. 10°-inclined slope which toe was interfingering with outer ramp marlstones. Massive grainstones of the Vicenza Stone formed in different parts of the platform, where differential diagenesis allowed for the preservation of open pore space.

Within the framework of the mapped geology, the climbing area of the Cliffs of Lumignano stands out as the key geological feature, that testifies for the paleogeography and ecological changes occurred here in the early Oligocene, i.e., the onset of a coral reef and of a large-scale carbonate ramp. The cliffs are then the main geoheritage element of the area. Along with it, other geoheritage elements could be identified and mapped, which mostly fall under the categories of exemplar outcrops, quarries of Pietra di Vicenza and caves.

Discussion/conclusions

Only the detailed mapping, and the careful distinction of lithofacies with paleoenvironmental significance, could highlight the geoh heritage value of the main geosites and geodiversity sites in Lumignano. This observation can be most likely generalized: since in Italy the coverage of geological maps is chronically lagging behind, it is still impossible to have a complete understanding of the Italian geoh heritage and geodiversity.

Figure 3. Geological map of Lumignano area (portion of Berici Hills, Vicenza, Northeastern Italy)

Yet, geosites and other elements of geoh heritage can be mapped, even regardless of their geomorphological value or contribution to the landscape and can be categorized by the type of geological characteristics and ranked according to their importance.

However, we refrain from attributing a local, regional, or national value, i.e., a degree of importance which is absolute on a national scale, to the mapped geosites. Such absolute rankings are likely subject to changes in function of the evolving criteria applied by local-national authorities and geological surveys, and as new geosites are found. This is a major problem especially for Italy, because the largely insufficient covering of the Italian territory with geological maps implies that many potential geosites are still to be found, and their discovery is likely to modify national rankings significantly. Instead, the relative value of geodiversity sites of similar type should be more stable.

For example, between two caves in the same area, the one that is larger, and bearing the most complete set of karst features, is always going to be ranked best. However, it might be awarded national importance in times when caves are highly valued (e.g., because of their geotouristic potential or because specific laws exist for their protection), or it may be ranked at a lower level of importance, if laws change, or larger and more representative caves are discovered elsewhere in Italy.

We thus suggest that the responsibility of absolute ranking should be left to regional or national authorities and be moderated by political decisions on, e.g., the degree of protection required for the geoh heritage and, consequently, the number of listed highest-rank geosites. Relative ranking of geodiversity sites may be instead added as an attribute to mapped elements of geoh heritage, since it can be based solely on scientific criteria and should remain stable against political or management decisions.

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